

The Interplay Between Religion and Politics and the Quest for Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

There has been a close affiliation between religion and politics in most parts of the world and epochs of civilization. They both involve systems of values and beliefs as well as systems of action which are justified in terms of these values and beliefs. They are important institutions to mankind, depending on how they are understood and practiced. In a country like Nigeria, where religion dominates almost every aspect of the national life, the positive significance of this religiosity should have been reflected in the political life of the country. However, past experience has often proved otherwise. This is why this paper interrogates the relationship between religion and politics in Nigeria's quest for development. This study employed the qualitative research design, with data gathered from secondary sources. The evaluative method was used to analyse the data. The study found out that there has been a gross disjoint between the praxis and tenets of religion and the political life of the Nigerian society. This has severely undermined Nigeria's quest for development. Perhaps this perfectly explains why disharmony, animosity, suspicions, disaccord, bigotry and hatred have become part and parcel of life in Nigeria. The study suggests that the adherents of the major religions should properly harness the religious diversity of the country for positive reasons. The political class should also desist from politicizing religion for their selfish ambitions. This paper concludes that a cordial and objective relationship between religion and politics has a capacity to engender the much needed development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Religion, Politics and Development.

Introduction

The relationship between religion and politics is an ancient one. In the great ancient civilizations of the world, kingship (representing politics) and priesthood (representing religion) were very closely related. At times it was not too clear whether one was dealing with a king with sacred powers, or a priest with political authority. The Priest-King was a common phenomenon. Examples cut across all continents: "the Egyptians in Africa; the Assyrians in the Middle East; the Greek and Roman Empires in Europe, and the Inkas in the Americas, to mention a few."¹ Similarly, in traditional African societies political life was interwoven with religion. The rulers were agents of the gods of the land and custodians of the wishes of the ancestors. The people, on their part, accepted the political arrangements governing their lives as religious obligations. Even modernity did not blur the relationship between religion and politics.

Like in most African countries, religion has been central to the political life of Nigeria. This should not come as a surprise as over and over, Nigerians have been described as incurably religious – a description that encompasses the entire African family. However, the extent to which this romance between religion and politics has helped in bringing about the desired overall development of the country remains a puzzle. This puzzle is quite complex and open to acute debate as the dynamics of events portray a devastating picture of the role religion has played in Nigerian politics. While opinions continue to differ on the issue of the relationship between religion and politics, present happenings have drawn the attention of the global community to the leading African state, Nigeria.

Suffice it to mention here that the concern of this paper is to evaluate the relationship between religion and politics in Nigeria and how this relationship could be positively harnessed. This concern has been given premium following the challenges rocking Nigeria in its quest for sustainable development and nation building.

In the long run, it is intended that this relationship should be redirected for sustainable development and peace in Nigeria and the world at large.

Religion and Politics in Nigeria

Religion and politics are two essential human institutions that shape human life. Nwanne projects this view when he rightly writes that “Both religion and politics regulate human behaviour: religion from moral perspective and politics from legal perspective.”² Right from the earliest civilizations in human history, these two institutions have been intertwined in that participation in societal life had religious colouration. For instance, in early Egyptian, Mesopotamian and Greek civilizations, religion groomed members who were to take key leadership position in the administration of the state. This goes a long way to suggest that politics and religion have long been co-operative in fostering the ideals of the common good in human society.

Like in every other society, in Nigeria, this relationship has also been evident. In traditional times, religion and politics were not separated; they were fused together. This is one feature that characterized traditional Nigerian societies and explains why religion keeps featuring prominently in the political life of Nigeria till this day. Commenting on this, Udoidem writes that:

Prior to the advent of the two foreign religions, Christianity and Islam, African Traditional Religion (ATR) had long been in existence. The religion permeated and ordered every aspect of life among Nigerian various nationalities. In fact, in most communities, there was no distinction between a religious action and a political action. All actions were rooted in their basic religious beliefs.³

Quoting Ikime, Udoidem continues that among Nigeria’s multifarious peoples, religion was inextricably mixed with government, the rituals performed by Yoruba and Benin *Obas*, the *Sarakuna* of Hausa land, the *Okpara, Obi, Eze* of Igbo, the *Amalosuwei or Amanyanabo* of the Ijaw, the *Ivie* or *Opakko* of the *Urhobo* and *Isoko*, or *Oku Ibom, Nsobom, Etebom or Obong* of the Ibibio and the Efiks .tc, were essential ingredients in the maintenance of political order, stability and the promotion of the people’s moral code.⁴ Udoh contributes to this when he comments that “in the past, our culture and religion provided for us checks and balances. There were religious as well as political institutions that curbed the excess of kings.”⁵ It was common place for traditional rulers to consult the deities of their communities in making key decisions affecting their communities. The chief priests/priestesses were the go-between the kings and gods. They had the authority to challenge the decisions made by the kings which were against those of the gods. This was enough for a vote of no confidence to be passed on the kings by members of their cabinets.

Going by the above background, one can understand why religion has remained phenomenal in the political life of Nigeria even after colonization that fused the different nationalities under a common political entity. As a matter of fact, these nationalities “had their own identity, system of government and religion and have endeavored to preserve them in spite of colonialism and the creation of the modern state of Nigeria.”⁶ It is no surprise that “today, religion has become the major defining factor of identity, particularly related to political identity in Nigeria.”⁷

It must be mentioned here that since after the amalgamation of Nigeria in 1914 leading up to the period of independence in 1960 and beyond, the religio-political climate of Nigeria has left more to be worried about than desired. Religion has not fared well in its relationship with politics. The experience has been that of conflicts and crises. This is because the relationship between the two dominant religions in Nigeria - Christianity and Islam - has gone confrontational and antagonistic than fraternal. Gwamna observes that “the 1970s marked a watershed in inter-religion relations in Nigeria. Since then, Nigeria has witnessed religious conflicts mostly between Christians and Muslims. Today religious competition between Christians and Muslims is without doubt the single most important political issue in the country. It has become a major factor of political identity.”⁸

Given the happenings in Nigeria, religion has become a point of suspicion because of the damage it has caused. In this light Jibrin submits that “religious brinkmanship has seriously damaged Nigeria’s body politics,

and appears to be more dangerous than previous ethnics and regional political conflicts.”⁹ It goes without asking why this has become the case. This, of course, has become mainly possible through two reciprocal influences between religion and politics namely, the politicization of religion and the religionization of politics. Such influences have always characterized the romance between religion and politics in a society of diversity like Nigeria, as seen below.

Politicization of Religion

The politicization of religion simply connotes making religion political and using it to pursue political interest in a way that is counter-productive. This is precisely the predominant game play in 21st century Nigeria. There is an acute manipulation of religion to achieve political interest. This manipulation has been responsible for the myriads of religious conflicts and crises in Nigeria. It is rather unfortunate as Ehioghae observes that in Nigeria, almost everything is politicized, even religion is politicized. Politicians are adept in playing on the people in order to accomplish their hidden agenda.¹⁰

He further states that, “reviewing the political process in Nigeria since the 1970s, it is easy to conclude that politicians have been using religion to gain political leverage. They hire religious fanatics and party thugs to perpetuate their dominance.¹¹ In the same vein, Ajayi observes that “...more often than not, aspiring political leaders laid and still lay more emphasis on psychological exploitation of the people’s religious affiliations than on the logicity and practicability of their manifestos, based on their individual credibility and merit.”¹²

Thus, the manipulative activities of politicians with regards to the religious sensibilities of Nigerians have given religion a bad name. This goes a long way to confirm the observation of Kimball when he avers that “it is somewhat trite, but nevertheless sadly true, to say that more wars have been waged, more people killed and these days more evil perpetrated in the name of religion than by any other institutional force in history.”¹³ In a related sphere, Ngele is right to have submitted that religion in Nigeria functions as a means for the perpetration of violence, fuelling ethnic consciousness and solidarity, acquisition of political power and socio-economic gains, massive killings and the wanton destruction of those considered infidels or who pay allegiance to other religions. This is traced to the acrimony between the dominant religions, Islam and Christianity, which have often resulted in the struggle for power and supremacy, bitter feud and wanton destruction of lives and property. This religious madness has like a cataclysmic vortex devastated the ground for sustainable development of Nigeria.¹⁴

It is not a matter of falsehood to hold that the politicization of religion in Nigeria has been a bane on its progress and development. The evident tensions have left much to be desired. These have come with telling consequences on the politics of the country. As a result of politicization of religion, there is constant conflict between the two dominant religions in Nigeria as each religion is out to present and protect its own candidates whether credible or not. It is indeed, no surprise as it is characteristic of religions to make strong claim on people’s allegiance. This puts religion in a condition where it can no longer play the role of the watchdog on politics. No religion is ready to discredit its adherents. When religion fails in its overall role of fostering morality and justice, chaos sets in. This is precisely the situation in Nigeria today. It is even worse when the situation becomes that of the religionization of politics for which attention will now be turned to.

Religionization of Politics

The religionization of politics emphasizes the utilization of politics for religious interests. Giroux referencing Zygmunt Bauman explains the religionization of politics as “a situation whereby secular politics and policy making will be reshaped by the logic and attitude of religious fundamentalis”¹⁵ This attitude is most evident in an atmosphere of religious diversity like Nigeria. The whole game plan becomes that of unhealthy competition between or among religions for supremacy. This is the attitude that is characteristic of Nigerian politics of the 21st century. Sincerely, it is not projected here that such has not been in Nigeria’s history; however, it has come to clarity in the 21st century. In this light, Nwanne observes that “our social, economic, cultural and political life has been revolutionalized courtesy of religion.”¹⁶ Religion which has become an architect than an antidote to

social unrest has killed many people under the canopy of politics. Majority of wars and crimes in Nigeria emanated from religious backgrounds.

In Nigeria today, one's religion determines his/her fate in the political game as religious organizations have divided themselves along political lines. Nwanneke's analysis gives a true picture of this. According to him; they (religious organizations) are gradually becoming political parties of their own. Religion now influences the voting pattern of people. A Christian is more likely to vote for a Christian than a Muslim even though that may be a death warrant to Nigeria's prosperity. In most churches and mosques, political campaigns are carried out as most of them have aligned themselves to different political parties.¹⁷ All this shows how religion now determines what happens in politics as political legitimacy is now dependent on religious affiliation and Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) and various forms of Nigerian Muslim Associations have failed to create equilibrium between political ideology, role and their religious ideology and duties."¹⁸ On certain occasion they have shown themselves to be agential in fuelling crises as each wing seeks not the common good but the wellbeing of its members. In this dynamics, the gap between Christians and Muslims keeps widening.

Expressing the extent religion and politics have manipulated each other, Udoidem asserts that "a careful analysis of the religious crises in Nigeria reveals that virtually all the crises were politically motivated and a careful study of most political actions show that they were masterminded by religious interests."¹⁹ It must be acknowledged with Kukah that Nigeria is not the first to experience the implications of religion in political choices. What makes these choices turn into weapons of destruction is the attendant characteristics such as poverty, squalor, illiteracy, hunger and want. A nation with these characteristics sees its population weakened and reduced to servitude and indignity. The citizens gradually fall back on patrons who then use the conviction of their so called constituency to engineer the people's conviction.²⁰ It is clear, then, how the masses are manipulated on religious identities built by their predators.

The issue of religion took a political dimension because each religion liked to have its members in position of power even if they were only nominal adherents of that religion. Through their adherents, each religion – Islam and Christianity, wanted to have its world view occupying the commanding position in the economic and socio-political scheme.²¹ Shortly before the 2015 elections, discussions had little to do with the credibility of the candidates as compared to their religious affiliations. The defection from one party to another had much to do with achieving this aim too. It was like asking the question, "which religion will man the affairs of this nation in the next dispensation?" The result of this attitude manifested itself in the formation of political parties, voting and the like which had religious interest intrinsically attached. One can understand why Kukah noted that "Nigerian politics even when pitched on other lines (North Vs South) always ends up being largely about Islam and Christianity."²²

The Challenge of Development in Nigeria

Various indices indicate that Nigeria is bedeviled by underdevelopment. The country is almost synonymous with abject poverty, grave malnutrition, disease, agonizing, violent, cancerous corruption and injustice. The Report of the African Commission (2020) corroborates this and asserts "Today Nigeria is a poor country in Africa. Half of the population lives on less than one dollar a day. Life expectancy is actually falling. People live, on average, to age of just 46. In India and Bangladesh, by contrast, that figure is a staggering 17 years higher."²³ It is in the light of this aphorism that Ogbonnaya observes that the challenges of Nigeria's underdevelopment are systematic. Things are going wrong on all corridors.²⁴ There are problems arising from poor governance and economic mismanagement, corruption and embezzlement of public funds. There are social upheavals arising from distorted border demarcations and combination of incompatible people. The consequences of the absorbing scenario have been nepotism, religious bigotry and ethnocentrism reflected in various conflicts across the country, all leading to underdevelopment. Thus, Nigerians variously face the problem of decaying available infrastructure and/or a total lack thereof, making it difficult for her to compete profitably in the global scene.

It is quite a paradox that while Nigeria's GNP increases, concomitantly her poverty level increases throwing more people below the poverty line of less than \$1 a day. According to a recent report on poverty headcount released by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), an incidence of poverty in Nigeria has continued to worsen between 2018 and 2023. The report indicates that the number of Nigerians living below poverty level has continued to rise within this period.²⁵ This paradox of growth in the form of poverty and inequity and injustice in Nigeria's socio-politico-economic distribution, with 1% of the population allocating the resources of the country to themselves while the rest of the populace wallow in abject poverty. In the face of such development backwardness that stares Nigerians in the face, how can religion be harnessed for integral development?

The Way Forward

The present relationship between religion and politics do not portend well for the developmental future of Nigeria. In this light, it is important to proffer suggestions for a more development-oriented relationship. First and foremost, there is a dire need for a limit to be drawn as to the extent that religion could properly feature in Nigerian politics given the fact of the country's religious diversity. There is need for Nigeria to make the provisions of the constitutions regarding religious incursion in politics and vice versa. In this regard there will be no room for either the politicization of religion or the religionization of politics.

As a matter of seriousness, adherents of the two leading religions in Nigeria must understand that neither of the two religions could freely dominate nor replace the other except they want to condemn themselves to permanent conflicts. As a result, the spirit of tolerance which is part and parcel of the two religions must be imbibed. As Wood proposes, "it should not be overlooked that there are explicit teachings of tolerance and condemnation of religious coercion and disrespect for religious views other than one's own to be found in major world religions."²⁶ Consequently, religious leaders must strive to always emphasize the aspects of their religions that foster more integration rather than division. Religious education involving all the religions in Nigeria should be made compulsory in all institutions of learning and attention should be paid to areas that foster integration in the said education.

In line with the suggestion of Benjamin Maiangwa in his suggestions of the management strategies as to the present Nigerian challenges in the religio-political sphere, the political parties in the country need to articulate their policies using the vernacular of patriotism in order to be able to work towards building a national political philosophy; efforts must also be made to achieve a more cohesive political class by making political parties in Nigeria more integrative. A step in this direction would be to limit the vast number of political parties in Nigeria in order to checkmate the inter-ethnic, inter-religious and inter-regional conflicts which have inundated Nigeria's political landscape since the attainment of independence in 1960.

Conclusion

Nigeria is one of the most religious nations in the world. This religiousness can be harnessed for the integral development of the country. This is because genuine religious spirituality respects human dignity, advocates for peace and tolerance, engages justice and fairness; makes for progress and development; encourages protection of lives and property; advances promotion of the communal good and creation of conditions conducive to human freedom and general development. However, past experiences in Nigeria have made many to conclude that religion instead of being an agent of development has, at different times, been an agent of decline, destruction, violence, and revenge. Religion has also impeded sustainable development by an unholy collaboration in corruption and mismanagement of the economy by religious leaders who have failed to challenge the unjust structures that give rise to bad governance in corruption and social malaise. Instead, various religious groups have often sought to benefit from the corruption and nepotism of the Nigerian system when a member of their religion is in power as the President or as the Governor or Chairman of the Local Government Area.

Yet, religion still has enormous roles to play towards the integral development of Nigeria. Religious leaders in Nigeria must figure out ways to honestly embrace peace and promote mutual coexistence so as to stem

the tide of religious fundamentalism that often is responsible for varying forms of violence that results not only in wanton destruction of lives and property, as well as cripples the economy and sets back the clock of integral development gained through many years of arduous labour, planning and creativity. It is only then that the role of religious relationship with politics for integral development in Nigeria will be transformed from a tale to reality.

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